

“INNOVATIVE APPROACHES AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF NEW GENERATION COMPETENCIES IN THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM.”

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***Annotation.** This article examines the role of innovative approaches in the modern education system and their impact on the development of new generation competencies. The study focuses on the application of innovative methods in English as a Second Language (ESL) teaching and their effectiveness in developing students’ communicative, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills.*

***Annotatsiya.** Ushbu maqolada zamonaviy ta’lim tizimida innovatsion yondashuvlarning o‘rni hamda ularning yangi avlod kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirishga ta’siri tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot ingliz tilini ikkinchi til sifatida o‘qitishda (ESL) innovatsion metodlarni qo‘llash hamda ularning talabalarning kommunikativ, tanqidiy fikrlash va muammolarni hal qilish ko‘nikmalarini rivojlantirishdagi samaradorligiga qaratilgan.*

***Аннотация.** В данной статье рассматривается роль инновационных подходов в современной системе образования и их влияние на развитие компетенций нового поколения. Исследование посвящено применению инновационных методов в преподавании английского языка как второго языка (ESL) и их эффективности в развитии коммуникативных навыков, критического мышления и способности решать проблемы у учащихся.*

Introduction:

The research explores how innovative approaches in modern education contribute to the development of new generation competencies, with particular reference to English language teaching at the Ministry of Internal Affairs Nukus Military Academic Lyceum “Temurbeklar Maktabi.”

The learning context is Military academic lyceum and the learners learn special military subjects and common subjects like English there. At the lyceum the learners are expected to show discipline, collaboration and better subject achievements because these are the important qualities for military jobs they want to gain in the future. Therefore, the learners are motivated to show their best versions in language learning and invest their time to develop their language skills.

However, their main challenges are related to writing skills because they do not have much practice in their writing. They need to work on their paragraph writing skills paying attention to the order of ideas like giving an opinion, explaining it and giving specific examples for it. Moreover, they should work on their summarizing skills because they listen a lot and they need to make certain conclusions on their listening materials. They are still challenged to make connections with what they have got as an input and what they produce as an output.

Introduce Your Text

Source:

Above Hustle (2022). *It will give you goosebumps: Cristiano Ronaldo motivational video. Greatest footballer all time.* YouTube. Taken from <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hvSDBX790rI&t=2s>

IT WILL GIVE YOU GOOSEBUMPS - Cristiano Ronaldo Motivational video | Greatest footballer All Time

Rationale and justification:

The video gives a motivational speech of Cristiano Ronaldo about his success which is based on his discipline. During his speech, he defines what discipline and dedication is for sports and for life. He highlights that there is no secret in success as anybody can achieve it if they are dedicated, disciplined and hardworking. Therefore, the video content is relevant to my learners who need to learn how to become disciplined. According to Maley (2014, as cited in Maley, 2016, p), an effective language teaching material should be relevant to the learners’ personal experience and my learners also are required to have discipline on their daily life at the lyceum. Therefore, listening to Cristiano’s discipline in English and following it in their daily life can be relevant to their life and learning at the same time.

Most importantly, the speech is given by a non-native English speaker because Portuguese is the first language for Cristiano Ronaldo. Therefore, learners can be exposed to different accents and forms of language in non-standard version, and this can address their listening challenge of understanding various accents and non-standard language forms.

I will use this video as a part of my writing activity. The main reason for choosing this skill is that my learners did not have much practice in writing and I have recently taught them how to write a paragraph by giving an opinion, explaining it and giving examples for it.

Activity Fully Developed

Writing activity: Paragraph writing

<p>Pre-activity: Watch a motivational video by Cristiano Ronaldo. Discuss and define <i>discipline</i> from Cristiano’s opinion.</p> <p>Activity: <i>Discipline is more important than talent.</i> Do you agree with Cristiano Ronaldo? Write a paragraph giving your opinion and supporting it with details from Cristiano Ronaldo. Write at least 80 words.</p> <p>Post-activity: Work in pairs and comment on your friend’s paragraph. Pay more attention to the paragraph structure (An opinion – giving explanation – giving example from Cristiano’s speech) and task response (Did your friend give his/her agreement or disagreement with Cristiano Ronaldo?)</p>
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Teacher guidelines version:

Pre-activity: [10min]

- Play a video of Cristiano Ronaldo describing discipline and its importance in one’s life.
- Organize a whole class discussion and have students define the meaning of the word “discipline” using Cristiano’s ideas.

Activity: [20min]

- Ask students to read the quote from Cristiano Ronaldo.
- Assign them to write a short opinion paragraph with 80 words with their personal opinion (whether they think that discipline is more important than talent or not) and supporting ideas from Cristiano’s speech.

Post-activity: [10min]

- Ask students to work in pairs and read each other’s paragraphs.
- Assign pairs to give comments on each other.
- Encourage students to pay more attention to paragraph structure and task response.

Video: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hvSDBX790rI&t=2s>

My learners also define “discipline” in discussions by gaining ideas from the speech and write their own position on whether discipline is more important in the life or not. This can enable them to use their communicative skills while relying on the points in the video. Therefore, the input I selected is comprehensible and relevant for my learners who are studying in military field and values discipline a lot.

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